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Pathogenesis of Herpes Zoster and Modern Solutions for Clinical Diagnosis

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***Abstract:** Herpes zoster or shingles is an infection that occurs when the herpes zoster virus reactivates after lying dormant in a nearby dorsal root ganglion. Symptoms usually begin with pain along the affected dermatome, followed by a vesicular rash that is usually diagnostic within 2-3 days. Treatment - antiviral medications are prescribed within 72 hours of the appearance of skin lesions.*

***Key words:** Clinical manifestations, Diagnostics, Treatment, Prevention*

Chickenpox and herpes zoster are caused by the Varicella zoster virus (human herpesvirus type 3); chickenpox is the acute primary phase of viral infection, and herpes zoster is a reactivation of the virus from a latent phase.

Herpes zoster affects the sensory roots of the ganglion, the skin of the associated dermatome, and sometimes the posterior and anterior horn processes of the gray matter, the pia mater, the dorsal and ventral roots. Herpes zoster occurs most often in the elderly and in people living with HIV, and is more common and severe in immunocompromised patients, since these patients have reduced cellular immunity. There are no specific factors that trigger exacerbations.

Signs and symptoms of herpes zoster

There is a shooting, dysesthetic, or other type of pain in the affected area, usually followed by a collection of blisters on an erythematous base after 2 to 3 days; Common sites are one or more contiguous dermatomes in the thoracic or lumbar region, but multiple associated lesions may also

occur. Lesions are usually unilateral and do not cross the midline of the body. The area is usually tender and may be painful. Lesions usually continue to form for about 3 to 5 days.

Herpes zoster (chest dermatome)

Herpes zoster (lumbar dermatome)

Shingles can spread to other areas of the skin and internal organs, especially in patients with immunodeficiency.

Herpes zoster (Ramsay-Hunt syndrome, geniculate ganglion syndrome) is the result of damage to the geniculate ganglion. Earache, facial paralysis, and sometimes dizziness occur. Blisters appear in the external auditory canal; taste sensations may be lost in the anterior two-thirds of the tongue.

Herpes zoster of the eye is a consequence of damage to the trigeminal (Gasserian) ganglion, accompanied by pain and vesicular rash around the eyes and forehead, which spreads along the ophthalmic nerve - the V1 branch of the 5th (trigeminal) cranial nerve. Eye diseases can be very serious. Blisters on the tip of the nose (Hutchinson's sign) indicate damage to the nasociliary nerve and the risk of developing serious eye diseases. However, in the absence of lesions on the tip of the nose, the eyes can be affected. If shingles spreads to the V1 region, consult an ophthalmologist.

Herpes zoster (along the V2 and V3 branches of the trigeminal nerve)

Herpes zoster (along the maxillary branch of the trigeminal nerve)

Oral herpes zoster is not common but may present as an acute unilateral lesion. There are no prodromal signs.

Reference materials on symptoms

1. Yawn BP, Wollan PC, Kurland MJ, St Sauver JL, Saddier P. Recurrence of herpes zoster is more common than previously reported. *Mayo Clin Proc* 86(2):88-93, 2011. doi:10.4065/mcp.2010.0618

Postherpetic neuralgia

Up to 6% of patients with herpes zoster will experience another episode of the disease (1), although this percentage may be higher in immunocompromised individuals. However, many patients, especially the elderly, may continue to experience local pain of varying intensity in the affected area for 3 months or more after the herpetic rash has resolved (postherpetic neuralgia).

Common sense and precautions

Less than 6% of patients with herpes zoster experience a relapse.

The pain of herpetic neuralgia can be sharp and intermittent or constant and debilitating. It can last for months, years, or forever.

Diagnosis of herpes zoster

History taking and physical examination

Herpes zoster is suspected even before the rash appears in patients with the characteristic rash and sometimes in patients with typical dermatomal pain. The diagnosis is usually based on the pathognomonic rash.

If the diagnosis is uncertain, the detection of multinucleated giant cells by Tzanck's test can confirm infection, but the Tzanck test is positive for both herpes zoster and herpes simplex. Herpes simplex

virus can cause almost the same lesions, but unlike herpes zoster, herpes simplex virus is prone to relapse and is not dermatomal. The viruses can be differentiated by cell culture or polymerase chain reaction (PCR). Antigen testing from a biopsy can also be used to diagnose herpes zoster.

Treatment of herpes zoster

Symptomatic treatment

Antiviral medications (acyclovir, famciclovir, valacyclovir), especially for immunocompromised patients

Moist compresses are soothing, but systemic analgesics are often necessary.

For the treatment of ocular herpes zoster, you should consult an ophthalmologist. For the treatment of herpes zoster of the ears, you should consult an otolaryngologist.

Antiviral therapy

Oral antiviral therapy reduces the severity and duration of acute outbreaks and reduces serious complications in immunocompromised patients; it may reduce the incidence of postherpetic neuralgia. In immunocompetent patients, antiviral therapy is often reserved for people over 50 years of age, who are more likely to benefit from treatment. Treatment is also indicated for patients with severe pain, facial rash, especially around the eyes, and immunocompromised patients.

Treatment of herpes zoster should be initiated as soon as possible, ideally during the prodromal period, and may be less effective if administered >72 hours after the onset of skin lesions, especially if no new lesions are appearing. Famciclovir and valacyclovir have better oral bioavailability than acyclovir and are therefore generally preferred for herpes zoster. Corticosteroids do not reduce the incidence of postherpetic neuralgia.

For patients with less severe forms of immunodeficiency, oral administration of famciclovir, valacyclovir, or acyclovir is appropriate; famciclovir and valacyclovir are preferred. Intravenous acyclovir is recommended for patients with severe immunodeficiency. Some experts recommend that immunodeficiency patients be treated for 7 to 10 days, continuing until all lesions have crusted over.

Although data on the safety of acyclovir and valacyclovir during pregnancy are encouraging, the safety of antiviral therapy during pregnancy has not been clearly established. Congenital varicella can result from maternal disease, but rarely from maternal herpes zoster. Therefore, the potential benefits of therapy in pregnant women should outweigh the potential risks to the fetus. Treatment with acyclovir is recommended for pregnant patients with severe rash, severe pain, or ocular herpes zoster, as there is more experience with its use during pregnancy than with other drugs, but valacyclovir remains an option. There are very few data on the safety of famciclovir during pregnancy, so it is not routinely recommended for pregnant women.

Treatment of postherpetic neuralgia

Herpetic neuralgia can be particularly difficult to control. Treatment includes gabapentin, pregabalin, cyclic antidepressants, topical capsaicin or lidocaine ointment, and botulinum toxin injections. Opiate analgesics may be needed. Intrathecal methylprednisolone may be helpful.

Prevention of herpes zoster

Recombinant herpes zoster vaccine is recommended for adults ≥ 50 years of age, regardless of whether they have had herpes zoster or have received an older live attenuated vaccine; 2 doses of recombinant

herpes zoster vaccine given 2 to 6 months apart (Advisory Committee on Immunization Practices for Herpes Zoster Vaccines), Recommended for adults ≥ 19 years of age who are or have been immunocompromised or immunosuppressed due to disease or therapy, including those with varicella, chickenpox, shingles, or herpes zoster (for more information: Recombinant herpes zoster vaccine in immunocompromised adults ≥ 19 years of age: Recommendations from the Advisory Committee on Immunization Practices—United States, 2022).

A post-marketing surveillance study found an increased risk of Guillain-Barre syndrome within 42 days of vaccination with recombinant herpes zoster vaccine, which has led some physicians to avoid using recombinant herpes zoster vaccine in patients with Guillain-Barre syndrome (see FDA requirements). This includes a warning about Guillain-Barre syndrome (GBS) in the Shingrix Medical Use Guidelines).

The previously developed live attenuated vaccine is no longer available in the United States, but it remains available in many other countries. The new recombinant vaccine provides much better and longer-lasting protection than the older, live attenuated zoster vaccine (which is a higher-dose version of the chickenpox vaccine). In a large clinical trial, the recombinant herpes zoster vaccine was 97% effective in preventing herpes zoster (1). The live attenuated vaccine is contraindicated in immunocompromised patients.

Prevention References

1. Lal H, Cunningham AL, Godeaux O, et al.: Efficacy of adjuvanted herpes zoster subunit vaccine in adults. *N Engl J Med* 372(22):2087-96, 2015. Epub 2015 Apr 28. PMID: 25916341. doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa1501184

Basic rules

Shingles is caused by the reactivation of the varicella-zoster virus (the cause of chickenpox) from a latent phase.

A painful rash, usually a mass of vesicles on an erythematous base, develops in one or more adjacent dermatomes.

Less than 4% of people have another flare-up of shingles, but many, especially older people, have persistent or intermittent pain for months or years (postherpetic neuralgia).

Antiviral agents (acyclovir, famciclovir, valacyclovir) are especially effective in patients with immunodeficiency.

Analgesics are often prescribed.

Adults ≥ 50 years of age and adults ≥ 19 years of age who are immunocompromised and at risk for herpes zoster should receive recombinant herpes zoster vaccine, regardless of whether they have had herpes zoster.

Additional Information

The following English language resource may be informative. Please note that the guide is not responsible for the content of this resource.

Recommendations of the Advisory Committee on Immunization Practices on the use of herpes zoster vaccines

Infectious mononucleosis is caused by the Epstein-Barr virus (EBV, human herpesvirus type 4), and presents with malaise, fever, pharyngitis, and enlarged lymph nodes. Severe malaise may persist for weeks or months. Serious complications, including respiratory failure, splenic rupture, and neurological syndromes, sometimes occur. Diagnosis is made by clinical or serological testing. Treatment is supportive.

Epstein-Barr virus is a herpes virus that infects 50% of children under the age of 5 (1). More than 90% of adults are seropositive for EBV. Its host is male.

EBV infection is usually asymptomatic.

(See general information about herpesvirus infections).

Pathophysiology of infectious mononucleosis

After exposure to the oral cavity, EBV infects B lymphocytes. Morphologically abnormal (atypical) lymphocytes develop primarily from CD8+ T cells that respond to infection.

After primary infection, Epstein-Barr virus remains in the host, primarily in B lymphocytes, for the rest of its life, after which an unstable, asymptomatic viral shedding occurs from oropharyngeal cells. The virus can be detected in the oropharyngeal secretions of 10–20% of healthy adults who are seropositive for Epstein-Barr virus (1). In immunocompromised patients (e.g., HIV-infected allograft recipients), shedding is increased and titers are elevated.

Epstein-Barr virus is not detected in environmental sources and is not very contagious.

Transmission routes

Transmission can occur through blood transfusions, but most often occurs through kissing between an uninfected person and a seropositive person who is asymptotically infected with Epstein-Barr virus. Only about 5% of patients acquire the virus from patients with acute infection (1).

Early childhood infection often occurs in lower socioeconomic groups and in crowded living conditions.

The Epstein-Barr virus is statistically associated with the following pathologies and may be a causative factor for them:

Epstein-Barr virus does not cause chronic fatigue syndrome. However, it rarely causes a syndrome that may include fever, interstitial pneumonitis, pancytopenia, hepatitis, or uveitis (i.e., chronically active EBV).

Signs and symptoms of infectious mononucleosis

In most young children, primary Epstein-Barr infection is asymptomatic. Symptoms of infectious mononucleosis often develop in older children and adults.

The incubation period is approximately 30-50 days. Fatigue can last for several months, but is usually most severe in the first 2-3 weeks.

Neurological complications are rare but may include encephalitis, seizures, Guillain-Barré syndrome, peripheral neuropathy, viral meningitis, myelitis, cranial nerve palsies, and psychosis. Encephalitis may present as cerebellar dysfunction and in some cases may be extensive and rapidly progressive, as in herpetic encephalitis, but is usually self-limiting.

Hemolytic anemia

Transient mild granulocytopenia or thrombocytopenia occurs in about 50% of patients; severe cases associated with bacterial infection or bleeding are less common. Hemolytic anemia is often caused by specific anti-I antibodies - cold agglutinins.

Splenic rupture can have serious consequences. Rupture may occur as a result of enlargement of the spleen and swelling of the capsule, which occurs at most 10-21 days after presentation. A history of trauma is present in only half of patients. Rupture is usually painful, but sometimes painless, leading to hypotension. For information on treatment, see Splenic Injury.

Respiratory complications rarely include upper airway obstruction due to pharyngeal or paratracheal lymphadenopathy; respiratory complications can be rapidly resolved with corticosteroids.

Hepatic complications include elevations in aminotransferase levels (approximately 2–3 times normal, returning to baseline within 3–4 weeks); these are seen in approximately 90% of patients (1). If jaundice or more pronounced elevations in enzyme levels are detected, other causes of hepatitis should be suspected.

Common and dangerous, Epstein-Barr infection occurs sporadically, but several cases can be noted in families, especially in those with X-linked lymphoproliferative syndrome. Survivors of primary EBV infection with lymphoproliferative syndrome are at risk of developing agammaglobulinemia or lymphoma.

List of used literature:

1. Johannsen EC, Kaye KM: Epstein-Barr virus (infectious mononucleosis, Epstein-Barr virus-associated malignancies, and other diseases). In Mandell, Douglas, and Bennett's Principles and Practice of Infectious Diseases (Ninth Edition), Elsevier, 2020, pp. 138, 1872-1890, 2020. ISBN: 9996119890, 9789996119897
2. Andryev S. et al. Experience with the use of memantine in the treatment of cognitive disorders //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 282-288.
3. Antsiborov S. et al. Association of dopaminergic receptors of peripheral blood lymphocytes with a risk of developing antipsychotic extrapyramidal diseases //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 29-35.
4. Asanova R. et al. Features of the treatment of patients with mental disorders and cardiovascular pathology //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 545-550.
5. Begbudiyevev M. et al. Integration of psychiatric care into primary care //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 551-557.
6. Bo'Riyev B. et al. Features of clinical and psychopathological examination of young children //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 558-563.
7. Borisova Y. et al. Concomitant mental disorders and social functioning of adults with high-functioning autism/asperger syndrome //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 36-41.
8. Ivanovich U. A. et al. Efficacy and tolerance of pharmacotherapy with antidepressants in non-psychotic depressions in combination with chronic brain ischemia //Science and Innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 12. – C. 409-414.

9. Nikolaevich R. A. et al. Comparative effectiveness of treatment of somatoform diseases in psychotherapeutic practice //Science and Innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 12. – C. 898-903.
10. Novikov A. et al. Alcohol dependence and manifestation of autoaggressive behavior in patients of different types //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 413-419.
11. Pachulia Y. et al. Assessment of the effect of psychopathic disorders on the dynamics of withdrawal syndrome in synthetic cannabinoid addiction //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 240-244.
12. Pachulia Y. et al. Neurobiological indicators of clinical status and prognosis of therapeutic response in patients with paroxysmal schizophrenia //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 385-391.
13. Pogosov A. et al. Multidisciplinary approach to the rehabilitation of patients with somatized personality development //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 245-251.
14. Pogosov A. et al. Rational choice of pharmacotherapy for senile dementia //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 230-235.
15. Pogosov S. et al. Gnostic disorders and their compensation in neuropsychological syndrome of vascular cognitive disorders in old age //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 258-264.
16. Pogosov S. et al. Prevention of adolescent drug abuse and prevention of yatrogenia during prophylaxis //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 392-397.
17. Pogosov S. et al. Psychogenetic properties of drug patients as risk factors for the formation of addiction //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 186-191.
18. Prostyakova N. et al. Changes in the postpsychotic period after acute polymorphic disorder //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 356-360.
19. Prostyakova N. et al. Issues of professional ethics in the treatment and management of patients with late dementia //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 158-165.
20. Prostyakova N. et al. Sadness and loss reactions as a risk of forming a relationship together //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 252-257.
21. Prostyakova N. et al. Strategy for early diagnosis with cardiovascular diseaseisomatized mental disorders //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 166-172.
22. Rotanov A. et al. Comparative effectiveness of treatment of somatoform diseases in psychotherapeutic practice //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 267-272.
23. Rotanov A. et al. Diagnosis of depressive and suicidal spectrum disorders in students of a secondary special education institution //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 309-315.
24. Rotanov A. et al. Elderly epilepsy: neurophysiological aspects of non-psychotic mental disorders //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 192-197.
25. Rotanov A. et al. Social, socio-cultural and behavioral risk factors for the spread of hiv infection //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 49-55.

26. Rotanov A. et al. Suicide and epidemiology and risk factors in oncological diseases //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 398-403.
27. Sedenkov V. et al. Clinical and socio-demographic characteristics of elderly patients with suicide attempts //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 273-277.
28. Sedenkov V. et al. Modern methods of diagnosing depressive disorders in neurotic and affective disorders //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 361-366.